

Collaborative skills among teachers at the schools as a predictor of their teaching performance in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The paper studied collaborative skills among teachers at the schools as a predictor of their teaching accomplishment in public secondary schooling in Delta State, Nigeria. 2 research questions and 2 null hypotheses raised to guide the study. The descriptive survey design was embraced. The population of this study consists of all 11,125 teachers distributed over the 477 public secondary schools in Delta State, out of which 390 teachers representing 5.32% of the population were used as respondents. A structured questionnaires titled: Teachers' Collaborative Skills for Job Performance Questionnaire was used to obtain data from the field. The reliability coefficients of the instruments (Social Interaction for Job Performance and Positive Interdependence for Job Performance, had 0.79 and 0.80, respectively were determined using Cronbach Alpha Statistics. mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions and the null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using z-test statistics. Findings revealed that teachers' social interaction for job performance and positive interdependence for job performance will improve and guarantee job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Delta State, Nigeria and these were found to be significant at 0.05 level of significance; Based on the findings of the study, and the discussions on them, it was concluded that appropriate teacher's collaborative skills will improve and guarantee effective job performance, it was recommended among others that to enhance further interrelationship, teachers should set up a collective goal, create recompenses for their success, and split the work-force of the conveyance of instruction.

Keywords: Collaboration, Collaborative skills, Delta State, Education, Nigeria, Teacher's job performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is considered a vital societal initiative that is essential for the advancement and progress of individuals and the collective community. It is widely known that the majority of developed countries have achieved this feat due to substantial investments in the education sector. This is because education as an industry perform a crucial part in the servicing of other sectors of the Nigerian economy. Therefore, every effort made to advance the education sector is a strategic move for sustainable development. This also explains why key attention is paid to the provision of necessary resources are essential for the administration of the education system, as they greatly define the quality of education. objectives that will be achieved in the short and long term. Human and material resources necessity be providing as required no matter the level of education for sustained developmental outcomes. One of the levels of education that is essential to the educational advancement of any nation is secondary education. Secondary education is strategic in the educational structure of any nation because it connects the other levels of education and makes it possible for the goals and objectives of primary and tertiary education to be achieved as an intervention system. Secondary schools help to correct the deficiencies of primary education and also equip students at this level for meaningful tertiary education. It is at this level of education that the deficiencies experienced at the cemental level of education are corrected. Education level therefore serves as a remediating platform and also prepares students at this level for higher levels of education. This is why the government and other stakeholders pay close attention to the activities at this level of education so that their educational expectations will not be jeopardized.

Secondary education aims to prepare students for life in society and further education. It also aims to provide them with the skills needed for effective living. The management of schools at this level is expected to be of good quality, promoting effective teaching and collaboration among teachers. The goals of secondary education are divided into three categories: providing opportunities for higher education, acquiring knowledge, and achieving successful teaching and learning outcomes. It is expected that by the time a student leaves secondary school, they will have acquired enough

knowledge and skills to be admitted to higher education or to be employable.

Collaboration involves entities sharing responsibilities to collectively plan, and assess a program of happenings to accomplish a shared objective. The originate idea after the Latin term "collaborate," which means "to work together," and represents shared creation, allowing entities to advance on each other's competences. It includes sharing responsibilities, and rewards, and can project a joint identity to an external observer if desired by the group. Collaboration requires the active participation of individuals to collectively solve challenges, which necessitates time, effort, and dedication. For instance, simultaneous engineering involves a squad of specialists collaboratively developing a new goods. This example illustrates that although coordination is necessary, collaboration also entails seeking diverse insights and spontaneity, rather than simply adhering to a structured harmony. As we transition from networking to collaboration, there's a greater level of shared obligation, and resources that members need to devote in the shared endeavour.

Collaboration is a complex process, and its success is contingent upon meeting several requirements: Collaboration should have a clear purpose, often focused on a common goal or issue to be addressed. It is not enough for each party to have their own targets. Fundamental necessities or prerequisites for collaboration consist of:

- All participants must consent to collaboration, which includes agreeing to share.
- All participants must comprehend members capabilities.
- All participants should share a goal and uphold a unified vision throughout the partnership process in pursuit of the shared goal.
- All parties must have a mutual understanding of the issue at hand, involving discussions about their progress (mutual awareness).

Sharing entails joint accountability for participation and policymaking, and mutual account for the outcome, as well as mutual trust. However, this does not necessarily mean that sharing is equality, as different participants may exhibit varying degrees of participation based on their involvement.

Collaboration involves various general steps as a process (Giesen, 2002):

- Identify the involved groups and bring all together.
- Establish the extent of the teamwork and the intended results.
- Establish guidelines for handling conflicts, accountability, and ownership of created assets.
- Establish assessment and valuation mechanisms and procedures.
- Identify dangers and develop exigence plans.
- Make a allegiance to collaborate.

Collaboration necessitates an environment that promotes and facilitates the collaboration procedure. The attributes and kind of this "space" depend on the type of collaboration. Collaboration can be either synchronous or asynchronous and can be collocated or remote/virtual.

Wolff (2005) put out key challenges in collaboration to include: resources, rewards, commitments, and responsibilities:

- Resources: Possession and allocation of resources pose a common challenge, whether it pertains to resources took in by members or resources secured by the alliance for the task.
- Rewards: Determining individual donations to join intellectual property manufacture is complex, as it does not have a linear relationship with the percentage of resources devoted by each member. This necessitates reaching a shared understanding of exchanged ethics, defining a benefits model, and creating an enticement system based on a mutual value system.
- Commitments: When faced with an dispute or obstacle, do members react as a unified group, or does each one seek to safeguard their own interests?
- Responsibilities: Diffusion of responsibility is standard in collective endeavors. Efficacious collaboration relies on sharing tasks during the process and liabilities after the collaboration concludes.

These various issues must be addressed through a common set of operating and sharing principles. Despite the challenges, the driving force behind collaboration is the anticipation of achieving outcomes that could not be attained by individual parties working in isolation.

The teacher's job performance in recent times has gone beyond just teaching in the classroom. In most schools today, teachers play both academic and administrative roles for the success of the school. It is not new for teachers to be deployed as members of committees such as counseling, disciplinary, etc. and they also attend stakeholder meetings within and outside the school on behalf of the school or the school administrator. The teacher is therefore expected to carry out all of these functions in line with laid down rules or plans. The teacher's performance can therefore be below, above, or at par with the guidelines. It is therefore common for teachers to seek the support of their colleagues to be able to carry out some of these functions effectively whether or not it is part of their direct duties in the school. The performance of teachers has a great impact on student's performance and the school as an organization. As such, everyone is always working hard to ensure that the teachers' performance meets the outlined educational aspirations. Teachers' job performance will...be more goal-oriented if they have cordial and good working relationships with other members of the school such as fellow teachers, students, principals, etc. However, the quality of the relationship that the teacher will maintain with these

stakeholders depends on the collaborative skills possessed by the teacher.

Two components facilitate collaborative processes: interpersonal skills, and monitoring progress:

Interpersonal skills are crucial for co-teachers, as verbal and nonverbal communication, building trust, managing conflicts, and finding creative solutions are all part of co-teaching. These abilities are crucial for effectively sharing leadership responsibilities and ensuring that every student receives attention. Co-teachers may possess varying levels of interpersonal skills, hanging on their coaching, personality, and communiqué preferences. It is essential for co-teachers to offer each other feedback and support so they can enhance their social skills.

Monitoring involves frequently discussing the achievements and tasks of collaborative teaching instructions. Co-teachers assess whether the scholars are meeting the lesson's education goals, evaluate their communication skills, and decide if any adjustments are needed in the learning activities. Monitoring methods can vary, such as using checklists or scheduling brief daily meetings to discuss these aspects.

Collaborative teaching methods include team effectiveness design, assessment of performance, brainstorming techniques, individual learning procedures within a team, research groups, and discussion methods. Collaborative teaching occurs when teachers work together to achieve shared teaching goals. It is an important area in education, with significant implications for theory, research, and practice.

1.1. Statement of the problem

Teachers of schools in Delta State are grouped into academic teams or departments to allow the exchange of ideas, and practices on how curriculum delivery should be improved for better learning outcomes. Teachers who attend different trainings are encouraged to share what they have been trained for with their fellow teachers at school for better site-based teacher training. Despite the presence of in-school department and in-service teacher training offered to teachers, the collaboration among teachers as an approach to effective continuous professional development appears not done effectively. The lack of effective collaboration among teachers results in low teachers' teaching performance. Then, having non-performing teachers in schools has a great impact on low student learning outcomes as none is supposed to give what she or he doesn't have. The beneficial and varied results arising from cooperative efforts have prompted multiple research investigations into cooperative education. These investigations concentrate on the prevention and management of a broad spectrum of societal issues, including diversity (racism, sexism, inclusion of individuals with disabilities), anti-social behavior (felony, drug abuse, intimidation, fierceness, impoliteness), Lack of prosocial values, egocentrism, feelings of alienation, psychological challenges, low self-esteem, and solitude are all areas in which one could benefit from support and personal growth. Co-operative education is viewed as the preferred instructional approach for the prevention and solution of numerous social issues affecting children, teenagers, and young adults. Hence, this study has been carried out to assess the collaborative skills among teachers at the schools as a predictor of their teaching performance, to come up with possible suggestions, and recommendations that will contribute to the improvement of site-based teacher training for better teacher performance to increase students learning outcomes.

1.2. Purpose of the study

This study examined the influence of collaborative skills among teachers at the schools as a predictor of their teaching performance in public secondary schooling in Delta State. Objectives include to:

1. find out the impact of teachers' interpersonal skills on job performance in public secondary schooling in Delta State, Nigeria.
2. examine teachers' monitoring co-teacher progress for job performance in public secondary schooling in Delta state, Nigeria.

1.3. Research questions

1. What are the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schooling in Delta State, Nigeria?
2. What are the ways teachers' monitoring co-teacher progress enhances job performance in public secondary schooling in Delta state, Nigeria?

1.4. Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Urban and Rural respondents in the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female respondents in the ways teachers' monitoring co-teachers' progress enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Education

The role of education in a country's economic development is crucial. Education is essential for providing the economy

with the skilled workforce needed to efficiently utilize resources and create high-value output. It is considered the foundation of economic and social progress and a key way to ensure the well-being of individuals. Education also plays a vital role in addressing societal growth and development challenges. Effective governance and educational services should be implemented from primary school through to higher education. Secondary education is place between elementary and higher education, making it a pivotal focus in this context. Investment in education is crucial for the development of a nation, and it plays a significant role in addressing key challenges to educational and developmental goals. According to Sophister (2015), education is an essential component of development and is necessary for both economic growth and sustainable development. Sustainable development, as defined by Shah (2008), is the type of development that fulfills present requirements without conceding the ability of future generations to attain their own desires. This idea encompasses not only material needs but also values, relationships, freedom, and the ability to live sustainably on moral and spiritual levels. Building positive interpersonal relationships through education is vital for achieving sustainable development. Education can be seen as an ongoing procedure of evolving the human mind, potential, and behaviours over continuous teaching and learning in conducive surroundings (Obomanu, 2011). The importance of good interpersonal relationships among teachers cannot be overstated, as it creates a favorable environment for job satisfaction. Overall, satisfaction involves meeting another person's needs, desires, and wishes to make them feel content and fulfilled. Satisfaction brings gratification, pleasure, and contentment.

2.2. Secondary education

Secondary education plays a critical role in Nigeria as it provides students with the foundation for higher education and practical skills for their future. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) has outlined the wide aim of secondary education to train students for convenient living in society and advanced level of education. Quality teachers are essential in achieving this aim. The management of schools at this level should be of high quality to ensure effective teaching and attainment of school goals, which include preparing students for higher education, knowledge acquisition, and teaching/learning outcomes. The goal is for students to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to either pursue further education or enter the workforce after leaving secondary school. This is why skill-oriented subjects are taught in secondary schools (Eto, Obeten & Obona, 2018).

2.3. Collaborative skills

The role that an individual plays in a specific context depends not only on their ability to collaborate but also on the roles of other team members and the requirements of the task. These roles involve differences in how much a person takes into account the perspectives of others, incorporates those perspectives into their ideas and processes, and effectively communicates and resolves conflicts with honesty and diplomacy. Not all roles may be necessary for a single task. For instance, if a task only requires generating ideas without prioritizing or making selections, there may be little need for coordination or conflict resolution. It's important to consider task demands when evaluating performance. Given the potential benefits of collaboration skills and their role in developing other skills, it's important to understand how to teach students these skills. There isn't evidence that simply increasing group work will improve collaboration skills. Instead, students need to practice and develop their collaboration skills by recognizing their mistakes and formulating strategies to improve (Rotherham & Willingham, 2010). Efficient teamwork necessitates dedication and entails multiple people working in tandem as equals to reach decisions that bring about positive transformations. Within an academic environment, collaboration strives to enhance services for students by uniting the efforts of families and schools as equal partners who mutually share resources, decisions, and responsibilities. Collaborative teamwork in educational institutions comprises five core elements as identified by Snell and Janney (2005), which encompass establishing team structure, acquiring teamwork skills, taking collective action, teaching collaboratively, improving communication, and managing conflicts. According to Bayat (2012), fundamental principles for fostering a partnership and cooperative relationship include communication, dedication, respect, professional proficiency, equality, and trust. Effective communication, attentive listening, and shared understanding between families and professionals play a crucial role in maximizing parental engagement. It is also important to discuss the specific educational and behavioral expectations and objectives for the child, express positive remarks about the child, and maintain regular communication with family members (Smith et al., 2012).

2.4. Teachers job performance

Based on Gable and Manning's (2009) findings, collaboration among professionals impacts educational practices and methods because teachers engage in shared planning, goal setting, collective decision-making, and program implementation to enhance effectiveness. Audu and Oliha (2008) stated that the morale of teachers is a crucial factor in the successful execution of educational programs. Moore (2005) believes that teaching ranks among the most stressful professions. Supporting this claim, a survey conducted by the Health and Safety Executive to gauge stress levels across various occupations found that teaching topped the list. Consequently, it is widely acknowledged that the workload for teachers is excessive. This is supported by the fact that while actual working hours may be shorter, teachers spend most

of their time preparing lessons, lesson plans, grading assignments, tests, or exams at home. Additionally, an analysis of calls made to the "Teacher Support Line" reveals that stress is the most common concern among teachers, with 27% falling into this category (Moore, 2005:2). However, through a relational process that fosters shared responsibility, the burden of stress is significantly reduced. The New Teacher Center (NTC) (2007) opposes that students educated by effective teachers outclass those taught by futile teachers. Onete, Udey and Ogbor (2011) assert that Nigerian teachers are under considerable stress. Armstrong (2009) reported that 87% of teachers experienced stress in the past two years, with 42% suffering from depression; 60% of these issues stemmed from workplace-related issues, 82% had sleep problems, and 53% lacked concentration.

Furthermore, it is noted that the extent and significance of health and well-being challenges in the teaching profession are evident. These issues are widespread and have a substantial impact on students, colleagues, and the individuals involved. Several participants argued that like other professions, teaching inevitably involves stress. Nonetheless, they all concur that immediate attention is required to address the causes and occurrences of stress in schools and government. It was emphasized that some of the most effective programs for reducing stress were found in the private sector, where employers openly acknowledge the potential for stress and actively provide and promote support to address it. Early identification of stress and other common health issues was deemed crucial for the success of such support, enabling individuals to take prompt action and prevent rapid deterioration. The Teacher Support Network (2005) reported that 80% of respondents have experienced work-related stress, which included panic attacks, workload, and workplace harassment. Ultimately, the motivation of teachers could significantly impact their work performance and effectiveness.

Nwachukwu (2011) suggests that motivation is essential for learning, and strategies should be developed to maintain an ongoing interactive motivational environment for maximum effectiveness. According to Bartell (1990), an effective educational environment can create a positive school climate where teachers and students feel comfortable with the learning process, fostering a caring attitude. The effectiveness of teachers can be greatly influenced by the availability of motivational responses. Therefore, Audu and Oliha (2008) also observe that high morale among teachers can positively affect students as well. Ultimately, motivation plays a vital role in enhancing teacher effectiveness, as whatever happens to teachers also affects students' learning outcomes. When teachers are motivated, they are likely to seek means to sustain the longevity of their professional practice, effectiveness, and productivity.

Educators and policymakers in the United States have been advocating for increased collaboration time for teachers in planning, administering, and evaluating their instruction. This push for collaboration is supported by numerous studies highlighting its benefits. There is no overarching theory that comprehensively explains the impact of teacher collaboration. However, evidence indicates that contented teachers tend to perform better, and social isolation can result in teacher dissatisfaction. By implementing collaboration and other necessary organizational changes, schools can diminish feelings of isolation, leading to improved student achievement, teacher job satisfaction, and teacher confidence. Additionally, research has demonstrated that teacher collaboration has a positive influence on student achievement.

Teachers who engage in collaboration benefit from an increased capacity for reflection, which gives them the opportunity to thoroughly analyze and address issues in their lessons. Through this process, they can discern effective and ineffective practices within their classrooms. As a result, teachers have reported that participating in collaborative interactions strengthens their confidence to experiment with new instructional techniques in their lessons and classrooms (Voelkel, Philip, Wik & Kyung, 2017). Importantly, even when teachers are not actively seeking to innovate, collaborating enhances their confidence and self-efficacy (Moolenaar, Slegers, & Daly, 2012). The cooperative nature of collaboration is particularly beneficial for bolstering the confidence of new teachers. By learning from experienced colleagues and understanding that they are not alone in facing challenges, novice teachers can increase their confidence (Carroll & Foster, 2008; Westheimer, 2008 as cited in Philip, Wik & Kyung, 2017).

2.5. Importance of communication on the teachers' collaborative skills

Effective communication skills are fundamental for teachers to support students in achieving academic success and preparing for professional success in the future. In the classroom, teachers primarily deliver instructions verbally to their students. A teacher with strong communication skills can significantly enhance a student's ability to learn and excel academically. Students must comprehend the principles of right and wrong, and this significantly relies on the effective communication skills of their teachers in the classroom (Sherwyn, Michael & Judy 2000). Positive communication minimizes the likelihood of negative emotions arising during the learning process. To facilitate effective learning, students must be attentive to their teacher during lectures. According to Loss (2000), it is recommended that teachers communicate clearly and understandably. Communication is a dynamic process that requires a sharp mind and the courage to engage with others and convey messages effectively.

Communication is the essential process of exchanging information, thoughts, and ideas among individuals. It involves various forms such as speaking, listening, writing, body language, and symbolic signs. Akinwale and Okotoni (2018) stress the vital role of the principal in fostering effective communication within a school. They emphasize that the principal should initiate innovative ideas and effectively communicate them to the staff and stakeholders, as well as share the school's vision and necessary information to ensure smooth operations. They also highlight the importance of

the principal's communication skills in conveying ideas and information to subordinates accurately and promptly.

Certainly! The skill set of communication covers various abilities, such as speaking effectively and fittingly, maintaining strong eye contact, actively listening, writing clearly and concisely, displaying confidence, empathy, friendliness, and openness, as well as eloquently presenting ideas (Manafa, 2018). Abbass (2014) emphasizes the crucial role of communication skills in ensuring that staff members fully understand their responsibilities and the expected standards. Zurita (2013) explores the complexities of communication within the classroom, portraying it as a multi-dimensional process influenced by the participants' social and ideological environment. In the field of education, communication goes beyond mere verbal interaction, involving the subtleties of expression and the development of a supportive teacher-student relationship.

2.6. Interpersonal skills

Teachers play a vital part in implementing educational policies at the classroom level, aiming to ensure that students can effectively navigate their learning environment. Abbasi and Hollman (2010) highlighted the diverse responsibilities of teachers, including providing guidance and counseling to students, managing classroom activities, and participating in curriculum development. Their motivation to excel in these roles is often heightened in environments where school principals exhibit strong interpersonal skills. Interpersonal skills are essential tools for effective communication and interaction within a structured environment. These skills reflect a person's proficiency in engaging with others and are instrumental in conflict resolution. Individuals develop and refine their interpersonal skills through interactions with family members, school experiences, and socializing with peers. Cultivating healthy interpersonal skills can lead to reduced stress, improved communication, enhanced intimacy, deeper understanding, and a sense of joy (Allison & Paolim, 2015). Interpersonal skills are the abilities needed to communicate effectively with others. Some authors have identified core areas essential for successful interactions within organizations. These skills are crucial for managerial success and have a significant impact on workforce performance and productivity. They are qualities people use in their daily interactions and are developed through experiences. Interpersonal skills include integrity, communication, responsibility, and teamwork. These skills are not innate but are acquired through training and experience. They play a vital role in determining a person's performance within an organization.

The term "interpersonal skills" encompasses a range of abilities related to social interaction and effective communication in professional settings. It is often used interchangeably with social skills and social competence, and its definition varies due to its pervasive influence. Fontana (2004) defines social skills as how individuals proficiently manage their professional relationships, emphasizing their pivotal role in various professions such as teaching, nursing, medicine, social work, management, law, and counseling. In the context of school management, interpersonal relationship skills are essential for school leaders to engage and collaborate with their subordinates to attain the school's objectives. Werang (2014) highlights how interpersonal skills empower leaders to influence groups toward achieving organizational goals. Moreover, these skills enable principals to demonstrate sensitivity and empathy towards teachers, fostering trust and considering their needs in aligning with the school's objectives. Ayeni (2014) underscores the importance of interpersonal skills in maintaining a positive work environment, as their absence can lead to strained relationships within the school organization, ultimately resulting in staff dissatisfaction.

2.7. Monitoring co-teachers progress

Monitoring is when managers and stakeholders regularly get feedback on how well a program is doing. It helps keep track of progress and can look at things like what's being done and what's been achieved. Monitoring uses this information to make decisions about how the program is going. It's aimed at improving how well things are working, making sure everything stays on track, checking that resources are being used properly, and providing a basis for evaluation.

Evaluating teaching means gathering feedback from different people to make teaching and learning more effective for educators and scholars. It's very important to keep an eye on the value of knowledge impacted in the classroom. The excellence of tutors has a big impact on the quality of education. Teachers are responsible for shaping students' behavior and thinking. Teachers play a key role in how much students learn at school. Good teachers help students learn well, while poor teaching can lead to lower achievement by students. Teachers play an essential part in determining the worth of education and its impact on the nation's development and economy. Students rely on their Teachers across all educational levels need to acquire the necessary skills for their future pursuits. Consequently, students view the personal attributes, educational background, and professional competence of their teachers as advantageous for their educational development. Recognizing the crucial role that teachers play, it is essential to supervise and assess their performance.

Teacher evaluation is a formal procedure implemented by schools to gauge and rank teachers' effectiveness in the classroom (Sawchuk, 2015). A thorough teacher evaluation entails accurately appraising teaching effectiveness, identifying strengths and areas for enhancement, and offering constructive feedback, guidance, support, and avenues for professional advancement. Evaluation provides valuable insights into how teachers fulfill their roles as facilitators of learning in the classroom, ultimately impacting students' learning achievements and their progress in acquiring essential skills and abilities. While monitoring and evaluation are often perceived as a combined concept, they serve different

purposes and encompass distinct functions.

The purpose of a successful evaluation is to produce valid and reliable outcomes, as well as to guide improvement. Evaluation can benefit students' learning in multiple ways. Firstly, it can help clarify the instructional objectives for both the teacher and the students. Secondly, the evaluation instrument can define how the objectives of instruction are to be achieved. Evaluation serves to address specific questions related to design, implementation, and results. According to Imas and Rist (2009), assessment can be used to address descriptive inquiries, such as determining current activities, as well as normative inquiries, such as comparing current activities with ideal ones. It evaluates operations to ascertain if goals are being achieved and contributes to ensuring quality. Particularly, formative evaluation is highlighted to ensure quality in secondary education. Formative evaluation should start with the establishment of a secondary school and continue throughout its existence with the purpose of advancing the teaching and learning process. The primary objective of secondary education is to cultivate individuals' intellectual capabilities and virtues for further education and practical living in society (FRN, 2008). Specifically, the secondary education system is designed to accommodate differences in abilities, opportunities, and future aspirations, providing practical knowledge and vocational skills essential for agricultural, industrial, commercial, and economic advancement. A secondary school should offer high-quality instruction and learning experiences.

Theoretical review

Systems theory, introduced by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy in 1968, explains the relationship between a whole system and its parts. According to Von Bertalanffy, it shows how the different parts within a system interact and depend on each other to perform various functions. This system includes an input (received from external sources), a transformation process, and an output (exiting the system). Similarly, the educational system operates with educational resources (both human and material) as the input, management techniques as the transformation process, and the resulting skills and the quality of graduates as the output. Zelvys (2004) defines a system as a collection of interconnected and interdependent parts, where the interaction of any part affects the entire system. Effective coordination among different individuals and units within the organization is crucial to achieving organizational goals. In the school system, students from diverse backgrounds are admitted as the input, and it is expected that school managers and teachers develop and implement strategic approaches for managing these students.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The researcher espoused a descriptive research design. The population of this study comprised of all eleven thousand one hundred and twenty-five teachers distributed over the four hundred and seventy-seven (477) public secondary schools in Delta State; with the number 5425 and 5700 being male and female teachers respectively. The sample size for this study was three hundred and seventy nine (379) teachers (respondents), this was obtained using the Taro Yamane minimum sample formula which gives the minimum number. The stratified Random Sampling Technique (SRST) was considered suitable because the researcher is dealing with a large population. A self-developed instrument is used as the medium through which data were obtained for this research. The instrument is titled: 'Teachers' Collaborative Skills for Job Performance Questionnaire (TCSJPQ). It was structured to contain two sections: Section A and Section B. Section A seeks information on the bio-data of the respondents, while Section B elicits information on Teachers' Collaborative Skills for Job Performance. The instrument used for this study was subjected to content and face validity was done by three experts. Three hundred and ninety (390) copies of the instruments were distributed and retrieved. Respondents were given one week to react to the statements in the instruments before retrieval, and 375 copies of the instruments were retrieved representing 94.5% of the instruments. The answers from the respondents were sorted, coded, and analyzed using SPSS. All the research questions were analysed using mean and standard deviation, and z-test was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question One: What are the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schooling in Delta State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

SN	Interpersonal Skills for Job Performance Variable	Respondents				Mean Set $\bar{X}_1\bar{X}_2$	Decision
		Male = 163		Female =212			
		$\bar{X}_1$	SD ₁	$\bar{X}_2$	SD ₂		
1	Separately from teaching, I attempt to solve any problems of other teachers.	3.09	0.90	3.19	0.87	3.14	Agreed
2	I appreciate good relations with my equals.	3.19	0.69	3.18	0.70		

3	I liaise with my equals in any exertion.	3.11	0.91	3.17	0.87	3.17	Agreed
4	For the improvement of my scholars, I contact other teachers and their parents to get a better knowledge of them	2.93	0.85	2.86	0.89	2.75	Agreed
5	I motivate other teachers to take part in co-curricular activities.	2.94	0.81	2.78	0.87	2.72	Agreed
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		3.05	0.83	3.03	0.84	3.04	

Data in Table 4.1 presents the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria. The results from items number 11 to 15, having the highest score in item number 12 at 3.17 and the lowest in item number 15 at 2.72, the average mean scores were 3.05 for the male and 3.03 for the female. Therefore, based on the average mean set score of 3.04 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, this implies that both male and female respondents agree on all the items (11-15) as the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: What are the ways teachers' monitoring co-teacher progress enhances job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the ways teachers' monitoring co-teacher progress enhances job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

SN	Monitoring Co-Teacher Progress for Job Performance Variable	Respondents				Mean Set $\bar{X}_1, \bar{X}_2$	Decision
		Male = 163		Female = 212			
		$\bar{X}_1$	SD ₁	$\bar{X}_2$	SD ₂		
6	Am challenged by the progress of others.	3.09	0.78	2.94	0.86	3.01	Agreed
7	We make more progress when we are closely working together.	2.91	0.87	2.84	0.90	2.87	Agreed
8	The performance of other teachers spurs me into action in the workplace.	3.12	0.61	3.04	0.71	3.08	Agreed
9	Teachers take time to observe each other's teaching during lesson study.	2.90	0.77	2.82	0.83	2.86	Agreed
10	I visit other teachers of the same subject I teach in neighboring schools for the improvement of my teaching.	2.69	0.86	2.68	0.94	2.68	Agreed
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.94	0.77	2.86	0.84	2.90	

Data in Table 4.2 presents the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the ways teachers' monitoring co-teacher progress enhances job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria. The results from item number 16 to 20, having the highest score in item number 18 with 3.08 and lowest in item number 20 with 2.68 the average mean scores were 2.94 for the male and 2.86 for the female. Based on the average mean set score of 2.90 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, it implies that both male and female respondents agree on items 16 to 20 on the ways teachers' monitoring co-teacher progress enhances job performance in public secondary schooling in Delta state, Nigeria.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Urban and Rural respondents in the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

Table 3: z-test Analysis on the Difference between the mean scores of Urban and Rural respondents in the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

Category	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Urban	314	3.05	0.83	373	0.17	±1.96	Not significant
Rural	61	3.03	0.84				Accept H ₀₃
Total	375						(z-cal. < z-crit.)

Table 4.3 the average mean rating/scores and standard deviation of Urban and Rural respondents stood at 3.05 and 0.83 and 3.03 and 0.84 respectively. Simple observation show that these mean scores differs from each other significantly. Furthermore, since at 373 degree of freedom and at 0.05 alpha level of significance, the calculated z-test value of 0.17 was less than the z-critical table value of 1.96, we were constrained to accept the null hypothesis and established that

significant difference do not exist between the mean ratings/scores of Urban and Rural respondents on the ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female respondents in the ways teachers' monitoring co-teachers' progress enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

Table 4: z-test Analysis on the Difference between the mean ratings/score of male and female respondents in the ways teachers' monitoring co-teachers' progress enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

Category	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Remarks
Male	283	2.94	0.77	373	0.813	±1.96	Not Significant
Female	92	2.86	0.86				Accept H ₀ ₄
Total	375						(z-cal.<z-crit.)

Table 4.4 the average mean rating/scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents stood at 2.94 and 0.77 and 2.86 and 0.86 respectively. Simple observation show that these mean scores differs from each other significantly. Furthermore, since at 373 degree of freedom and at 0.05 alpha level of significance, the calculated z-test value of 0.81 was less than the z-critical table value of 1.96, we were constrained to accept the null hypothesis and established that significant difference do not exist between the mean ratings/scores of male and female respondents on the ways teachers' monitoring co-teachers' progress enhance job performance in public secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Teachers' Interpersonal Skills enhances Job Performance

The third finding of this study revealed both male and female teachers agreed in all the items (11-15) as ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhances job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. These include: Apart from teaching I try to solve any problem of other teachers, they enjoy good relations with my colleagues, they co-operate with my colleagues in any work, for the betterment of my students I contact other teachers and their parents so as to get better knowledge of them and they motivate other teachers to take part in co-curricular activities. In addition, the finding show that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of urban and rural respondents on ways teachers' interpersonal skills enhances job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The finding is in line with Hargie and Dickson (2014) who agreed on a number of core areas in which competency is essential for effective interpersonal interactions among the internal and external stakeholders of the organization. Interpersonal skills, which are also identified as essential skills, are the critical skills that demonstrate interpersonal competence and organizational communication effectiveness which are essential for managerial or administrative success.

5.2. Teachers' Monitoring Co-Teacher Progress for Job Performance

The fourth finding of this study revealed that male and female teachers agreed in items 16-20 as the ways teachers' monitoring co-teacher progress enhances job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. These include; they challenged by the progress of others, they make more progress when we are closely working together, performance of others teachers spurs me into action in the work place, teachers take time to observe each other's teaching during lesson study, and they visit other teachers of the same subject I teach in neighboring schools for the improvement of my teaching. The finding also show that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female respondents on ways teachers' monitoring co-teachers' progress enhances job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. The finding is in consonance with Vipene, Joseph and Kerene (2021) who carried out study on monitoring and evaluation of teachers as determinants of quality assurance in secondary education in Rivers State. The study investigated Monitoring and Evaluation of Teachers as Determinants of Quality Assurance in Secondary Education in Rivers State. Findings from the study revealed there is significant difference in the mean ratings of principals, vice principals administration and zonal directors supervision on the extent teachers supervision enhance quality assurance in secondary school education. Thus Teachers' supervision enhances quality assurance in secondary school education, principals, vice principals administration and zonal directors supervision agreed to a high extent that instructional strategies adopted by teachers enhance quality assurance in secondary school education. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made, that the supervising authorities should regularly supervise teachers to ensure proper instructional delivery that will enhance quality assurance in secondary education, teachers should cultivate creativity in their teaching as to be successful in their teaching career and teachers should Explore an inclusive approach to teaching, the popular method of teaching such as lecture and discussion methods should be ignore and engage other innovative methods that promote critical thinking, creativity and productivity among students as to enhance quality assurance in secondary school education in Rivers State.

6. CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

This study has contributed to knowledge in the sense that it has brought to limelight various teachers' collaborative skills that will enhance teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria.

7. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study if put in use, would be of great benefit to the Ministry of Education, future researchers, the Government, teachers, school administrators, and the members of the public in several ways. The outcome of this study will enable teachers to identify the combination of collaborative skills that they can adopt in their place of assignment to improve their teaching performance for effective service delivery.

8. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that appropriate teacher collaborative skills will improve and guarantee effective job performance, therefore it is necessary for the government of the state and all relevant stakeholders in the education sector to provide good plans for continuous teacher development programs in the area of collaborative skills and provide workshops and seminars for educators in public secondary schooling in Delta State, Nigeria.

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